

KEY ROLE OF QUBE CE'UMSA RING IN OPENING GUUBOO AYYANTU DEVICES OF SCIENCE EDUCATION

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December, 31, 2022

ABSTRACT

Practical technique allow educators for introducing practical teaching of physics in secondary and primary schools remains a mystery just like the main cause of Blazhko effects, even in today world. Guuboo Ayyantu devices of science education were invented in 2020 to solve the problem from a grass root. Cushitic pyramid, Cartesian bed room, five rings of Cushitic cultural Astronomy (finger ring, ear ring, bracelet, Leg ring and necklace ring), Namoratonga Pillar and Abba Geda Stick are the major models of the device. Initially, the indigenous knowledge oriented device has 15 elements analogous to 19 basalts of Namoratonga pillar that invented 2300 years ago by Ayyantu Imaging technique. GA ring is its 16th element recently invented for solving challenge of cultural invention. Qubee Ce'umsa ring 17th element of the device resulted from 16th element. Qubee Ce'umsa is six Afaan Oromoo Qubee recorded on triangular element of the initial device. Above 15 researchers have been finding the scientific method needed to open the device. Among the elements of the device **Qube Ce'umsa ring** was used in implementing **science for society** proposed to deliver community service with follow up of Dambi Dollo University and 5 selected schools. The invention of this element was begun in the last two months by five (5) inventors of **Oda Star Triangles**. *Percentage of error of the scientific output achieved by analyzing the raw data taken from the device with proper measurement is less than 1%*. Thus, the community service team has already identified that the newly invented element of Guuboo Ayyantu devices of science education motivates secondary school students, teachers and decision makers to implement practical physics by solving the previous shortage of laboratory devices and guidelines allow education centers to do so. **The present work focused to communicate how the device integrating Cushitic cultural Astronomy records with practical physics. Moreover, this work intended to interpret the necessity of implementing community service proposed by Ayyantu Box Science and Invention Network (ABSIN).** The newly invented element (including its laboratory guide line), finger ring, coin, meter stick and thin thread are materials supporting the present work. The circumferences of three circular objects were measured using thin thread and meter sick. Diameters of each object were also measured using meter stick. The ratio of the former parameter to the second was computed using mathematical model $\pi = C/D$, where C-represents circumference of any circle and D is its diameter. The researchers identified how the indigenous device digging out how Cushitic Cultural Astronomy was integrated to science and mathematics.